

THE CONCEPT “FRIENDSHIP” IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE VIEW OF WORLD THROUGH THE PRISM OF PROVERBS AND SAYINGS

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The national character of the proverbs and sayings of the English people is determined by their way of life, working conditions and traditions. With the help of proverbs and sayings, we can imagine nationally determined identity in the worldview of the people, in relation to work, family, and friendship.

Proverbs and sayings of the English language that describe friendship are characterized by the presence of universal proverbial expressions, which in etymological terms are borrowings from biblical texts, classical languages, mutual tracings, etc. Examples include the following English proverbs and sayings:

Love me, love my dog;

Dog doesn't eat dog;

Better an open enemy than a false friend;

Greater love hath no man than this, that a man lay down his life for his friends;

If you lie down with dogs, you will get up with;

Short reckonings make long friends;

God defend me from my friends; from my enemies I can defend myself;

English proverbs and sayings reflect the idea mutual understanding and help, unity in everything, a common share, for example: Not is a good friend that speaks well of us behind our backs; In addition, in English proverbs and sayings the idea of falsehood in sweet speeches is noted: All are not friends that speak us fair.

The most frequently represented proverbs and sayings are in which the value component of the concept of “friendship” is brought to the fore. Most often this is achieved through comparison:

It's merry when friends meet;

Better lose a jest than a friend;

A friend in the market is better than money in the chest;

One God, no more, but friends good store;

It is good to have some friends both in heaven and hell;

Friends tie their purse with a cobweb thread;

No physician like a true friend;
They are rich who have true friends;
When friends meet, hearts warm;
A friend in court is better than a penny in purse;
One enemy is too many; and a hundred friends too few;
A true friend is the best possession [2: 278]

In addition, there are common English proverbs and sayings that describe the concept “Friendship”, and which indicate the danger of false friendship built on a monetary basis. In accordance with it, only wealthy rich people, “happy” people have many friends, while the poor and “unfortunate” bear their burdens on their own, this is expressed in proverbs such as:

When good cheer is lacking, friend will be packing;
While the pot boils friendship blooms;
Rich folk have many friends;
No friendship is strong that owes its rise to a pot;
Friends through fortune become enemies through mishap;
Poverty parts fellowship;
A false friend and a shadow attend only while the sun shines;
Misfortune makes foes of friends;

Also, in the English language there are proverbs and sayings, in which correlates friendship and deeds, for example:

One good turn deserves another Scratch my back, and I’ll scratch yours;
A hedge between keeps friendship green;
Roll my log, and I’ll roll yours [4:424]

A number of English proverbs and sayings describe the causal aspects of the loss of friendship due to its vulnerability and fragility. The considered proverbs and sayings warn people against causing irreparable damage from rash actions and words, for example:

A broken friendship may be soldered, but will never be sound;
When love puts in, friendship is gone;
One may mend a tom friendship but it soon falls in tatters;
A friend is not so soon gotten as lost;
Lend your money and lose your friend [3: 478]

In addition, in English proverbs and sayings, the concept of “friend” within itself develops such meanings as “a trusted friend” and “a friend who at any moment may turn out to be an enemy,” which is expressed in such proverbs as:

A broken friendship may be soldered but will never be sound;

A cracked bell can never sound well;

Thanks to the opposition “friendship - enmity” illustrates the multidirectionality of the power that these proverbs and sayings possess: Concord makes small things grow;

Thus, in particular, the concept of “quarrel” is not simply illustrated as such, but also adds consideration of the reasons why friendship can become enmity. Among these are money (debts), betrayal and lies (gossip), this is expressed in the following proverbs and sayings:

Lend your money and lose your friend;

One cannot run with the hare and hunt with the hounds;

He is a good friend who speaks well of us behind our backs;

Many English proverbs and sayings talk about proven, “old” friendship, which is contrasted with short-lived, for example:

Friendship, the older it grows, the stronger it is;

Old friends and old wine and old gold are the best;

Old fish, old oil, and an old friend are the best;

Old acquaintances will soon be remembered;

The best mirror is an old friend [1: 472]

The composition of the semantic structure of proverbs and sayings of the English language includes unique components that determine the nationally specific semantics of the word “friendship”, relating mainly to those aimed at finding and preserving it, for example:

Friendship increases in visiting friends, but in visiting them seldom;

Friends are like fiddle-strings, they mustn't be screwed too tight;

No man has a worse friend than he brings with him from home;

Thus, the analysis of English proverbs and sayings describing the concept of “friendship” showed that the British treat friendship with special trepidation, value old, true friendship and forbid hypocritical friends.

Having analyzed the selected proverbs and sayings of the English people dedicated to work, friendship, family and home, we can draw the following conclusions:

1) many English proverbs and sayings in which the value component of the concept of “friendship” is brought to the fore;

2) the British treat friendship with special reverence, value old friends, honor true friendship and forbid hypocritical friends;

In conclusion, English proverbs and sayings, expressing such concepts as work, friendship, family and work, allowed us to more deeply understand the national traditions, customs, life, way of life and worldview of the English people.

Reference:

1. Howatch S. Scandalous Risks. – N. Y.: Corgi Books, 1990 – 472 p.
2. Johnson L. Dangerous minds. – N. Y.: St. Martin's Paperbacks, 1993. – 278 p
3. Lehane D. Mystic River. – N. Y.: Harper Torch, 2002. – 478 p.
4. Sheringham S. Cuckoo in the nest. – London: New English Library, Hodder and Stoughton, 1991. – 424 p